

PERCEPTION AND EXPECTATION OF SERVICE AND MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY TOWARDS GST RULING AND DOCUMENTATION – A STUDY IN BENGALURU

Dr. MANJUNTHA BV, Assistant Professor, JAIN (deemed to be University), Bangalore

Mrs. TEJASWINI, Assistant Professor, JAIN (deemed to be University), Bangalore

Ms. NOMPI RAJ, Assistant Professor, JAIN (deemed to be University), Bangalore

Mrs. MEENU SUBRAMANYA, Assistant Professor, JAIN (deemed to be University), Bangalore

ABSTRACT:

Implementation of GST is the main taxation reform happened in the history of Indian Taxation System which leads to abolition of previous indirect taxation and implement Canadian type of (Dual taxation) indirect taxation in Indian economy. Changes and modification are the part of business environment in any economy which makes industries uncomfortable in the beginning of the changes. GST has brought changes drastically in terms of indirect taxation by replacing many types of indirect taxation like VAT, Excise duty, State tax etc., in the economy with which industries felt uncomfortable and expected few changes in the indirect taxation system.

KEY WORDS: Input Tax Credit, E – Way Bill, Documentation, Credit Note, Advanced Ruling.

1. INTRODUCTION:

India is one of the major developing economies in the world and 7th largest economy in terms of GDP (IBEF 2021-2022). India is with rich cultural heritage which includes different languages and traditions the country always holds its uniqueness in its diversity, and hence has adapted to international changes and challenges with dignity and comfort. Three main sectors in Indian economy are Agricultural sector, Service sector and Manufacturing sectors are contributing more for the development of economy. At present, service sector is contributing around 67.17% of the Indian GDP (at current prices) in 2021-22 (RBI Database - 2022). In order to make economy strong state is framing various industrial policies and amending the existing policies whenever it is required. Dynamism is the main feature of business environment of India which makes the state to adopt necessary changes for identifying economy among the top economies in the world.

Chart 1: Showing GST collection in 2019-20 and 2020-2021

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Taxation income is the main income for all the countries in the world in order to develop the infrastructure facilities and meet other developments in the economy. The normal situation in the economy always helps the industries to perform well which leads to manufacture and sell more. Every new change in the guidelines and regulations are the challenges to regulating authority starting from implementation till evaluation and revision. It is also a challenge for industries to receive the new and adopt the same in their system. GST in India has brought many changes to the previous indirect taxation including documentation, input tax credit, refund etc. but how industries in India reacted to all the changes took place in the area of GST is the concentration point.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ernst & Young, (2006) the authors have carried out a study for the European Commission – Directorate General of Customs and Indirect Taxation. The study is in relation to taxation of financial and insurance services under the VAT system. It studies the different approaches like cash flow method, subtraction method etc. The paper discusses the taxability of gold transactions under VAT. Further it is suggested that for financial services where there is no physical delivery involved the same should not be liable to VAT. The paper does emphasize

that for taxing financial services having explicit place of supply of services rules is essential. **Feria, (2010)** the authors have evaluated the European Commission's proposals in relation to reforming the VAT applicable on financial services. The issues arise in VAT and financial services due to the fact that the margin or return on financial services is both for lending the money and for bringing the lender and borrower together. However, it is almost impossible to segregate the return for each individually. For this EU had also explored the option of following the 'cash-flow' method to tax financial services. But this had too many practical problems mainly that of very high compliance costs. The paper primarily discussed the proposal to allow member states to 'opt-in' and tax the financial services so that ITC is available. The paper concludes that the practical implementation of the same is quite difficult. **FICCI, (2013)** in this paper, the authors through FICCI, a body representing the industry, have explained the approach to the proposed GST and have discussed the same along with recommendations from FICCI. FICCI believes that GST as a tax would lead to increase in the efficiency of the Indian economy, reduce the costs and efforts of compliance, increase the overall revenues and simplify tax administration. Based on these expectations, FICCI has placed these recommendations orally and through writing before the government. Basically, the recommendations include points like no exemptions to be granted (eg – petroleum should also be liable to GST), state and local bodies should not have authority to impose additional taxes once GST is introduced. Further, the states may have an option of not adopting GST till they want, but once adopted they should not be given the option of quitting. **Gale, (2011)** The authors in this paper have discussed how a federal VAT could be a potential solution for the fiscal deficit problem in United States of America. The paper discussed the ideal VAT that could be introduced in USA based on the Canadian experience. The authors have discussed the yield ratio, which indicates the ratio of the increase in VAT revenues as a part of GDP due to an increase in the VAT rate. This would be positive for the USA and help in reducing the deficit. The authors have also given comparative statistics for other OECD countries also to show how VAT helps generate revenues for the government. The authors have also discussed the benefits and drawbacks of zero rating certain preferred goods or making them exempt. **Gelardi (2013)** The author in the paper has studied the expected impact on consumers of the proposed National Consumption Tax to be introduced in USA since it would mean additional costs to the consumers. This proposed tax would be federal and in addition to the existing state sales tax in the various states of the US. For this study, UK and Canada where the VAT or GST a similar tax on consumption, is already operative has been studied to see the change in consumer behavior with introduction of these taxes. The author concludes that there is not substantial impact on consumer behavior due to introduction of these consumption taxes, however the rates of these taxes do impact the same in UK and Canada. If the rate change is major in these taxes, marked change in consumer behavior is also observed. **KPMG, (2012)** KPMG has in this paper, summarized its views on the VAT provisions as applicable in Philippines as of October 2011. The paper lists out the relevant provisions and provides brief synopsis of how they operate in Philippines. Basically, in Philippines VAT is a tax which is applied on consumption, sale, barter, exchange or lease of goods and services within Philippines or imported into Philippines. Services which are imported into Philippines are liable to VAT in the country since it is considered that the

services are performed in the country. Thus, services exported from Philippines are considered as performed outside the country hence not liable to VAT. This is relevant in services since the same are intangible.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- i. To know the perception of industries towards GST regulations
- ii. To study the expectation of Industries in modification of existing rule in GST.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive and analytical method of research is used to collect the opinion of industries. Primary and secondary data are used in this research. Convenience method of sampling is used select manufacturing and service industries in Bangalore.

6. ANALYSIS

1. Frequency and percentage of Distribution on the expectation by the organizations to change in GST rule. Result of test statistics as follows

Table 1: Showing the expectation of respondents to change in GST system

Changes	Type of organization				Total Count
	Service		Manufacturing		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Input tax credit	334	66	345	55	679
	83.5%	16.5%	86.25%	13.75%	84.75%
Place of supply	343	57	342	58	685
	85.75%	14.25%	85.5%	14.5%	85.6%
Return	12	388	9	391	21
	3%	97%	2.3%	97.7%	0.26%
Credit Note/Debit Note	32	368	36	464	68
	8%	92%	9%	91%	0.85%
Refunds	57	343		319	136
	14.25%	85.75	20.25%	79.75%	0.17%
Documentation	51	349	62	338	113
	12.75%	87.25%	15.5%	84.5%	14.12%
Advance Ruling	67	333	54	346	121
	16.8%	83.25	13.5%	86.5%	15.12%
E-way bill	3	397	42	358	45
	0.75%	99.25%	10.5%	89.5%	
Total	400		400		

The companies were asked to give their opinion on the expected changes to overcome the problems faced by them in Input tax credit, filing of Return, Refund claim, etc. and the information obtained from them is given in the above table. It may be noted that 334 companies (83.5%) in service sector and 345 companies (86.3%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Input tax credit; 343 companies (85.8%) in service sector and 342 companies (85.5%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Place of supply; 12 companies (3%) in service sector and 9 companies (2.3%) in manufacturing sector want changes in filing of Return; 32 companies (8%) in service sector and 36 companies (9%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Credit Note / Debit Note; 51 companies (12.8%) in service sector and 62 companies (15.5%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Documentation; 67 companies (16.8%) in service sector and 54 companies (13.5%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Advance Ruling; 3 companies (1%) in service sector and 42 companies (10.5%) in manufacturing sector want changes in E-way bill offences. It is evident that the companies are expecting changes mainly in Input tax credit and Place of supply.

2. Expectation to change in Input Tax Credit : Frequency and percentage of Distribution in expectation to change in ITC. The results are as follows.

Chart: 2: Showing expectation in changes to ITC

The companies were asked to give their opinion on the expected changes to overcome the problems faced by them in Input tax credit the information obtained from them is given in the above table. It may be noted that 334 companies (83.5%) in service sector and 345 companies (86.3%) in manufacturing sector want changes in Input tax credit.

3. Expectation to change place of supply: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in expectation to change the place of supply. The results are as follows.

Chart 3: Showing expectation change place of supply

It is clear from the above analysis that most of the respondents are expecting changes in place of supply.

4. Expectation to change in the return procedure: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in expectation to change in GST return procedure. The results are as follows.

Chart 4: Showing expectation change place of supply

It is clear from the above analysis that very smaller numbers of respondents from both the sector are expecting changes in return. 97% of the respondents from the service sector and 97.7% respondents from the manufacturing sectors are happy with the present GST return procedures. The GST return is the process of calculation of total tax liability and payment of GST. The 39th GST council meeting has brought changes in GST return which has made return of GST easier.

5. Expectation to change in debit note and credit note procedures: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in expectation to change in debit note and credit note procedure. The results are as follows.

Chart 5: Showing expectation change in debit note and credit note

It is clear from the above chart that 92% from the service sector and 91% from the manufacturing sector are happy with the present debit and credit note procedures.

6. Expectation to change in refund process and procedures: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in refund procedure. The results are as follows.

Chart 6: Showing expectations to changes in refund procedures

Most of the respondents from both manufacturing and service sectors are not expecting changes in the present GST refund procedures since it is easy for organizations to claim the refund. 85.75% from the service sector 79.75% from the manufacturing sector are happy with the present refund process hence not expecting changes.

7. Expectation to change in GST documentation: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in GST documentation is analyzed and results are as follows.

Chart 7: Showing expectation to changes in GST documentation

It is clear from the above chart that 85.75% respondents from service sector and 79.75% from manufacturing sector are happy with the GST documentation procedure and expecting no changes in the present GST documentation system. Documentation is the process of arranging and submitting the required documents at the time of filing and getting refund. The GST council has made documentation process easier for the organizations.

8. Expectation to change in the process of GST advance ruling: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in GST advance ruling is analyzed and results are as follows.

Chart 8: Showing expectation to changes in GST advance ruling.

It is clear from the above analysis that 83.25% of the respondents from the service sector and 84.5% from the manufacturing sector are not expecting any changes to be done in the process of advance ruling which helps in solving many doubts of tax payers under GST system

9. Expectation to change in E way bill offences: Frequency and percentage of Distribution in GST E-way bill offences is analyzed and results are as follows.

Chart 9: Showing expectation to changes in GST E-way bill offences.

It is clear from the above chart that E-Way bill mechanism system is greatly accepted by the 99.25% of service sector respondents and 89.5% of the manufacturing sector respondents who are not expecting in the present E-way bill mechanism.

7. CONCLUSION:

GST system in India is the revolution in the history of Indian taxation system which has brought reforms in the process of documentation, Input Tax Credit, Refund etc. Industries in India had many struggles in the beginning of GST and it was tough for them to adopt the new regulation in different process but GST council meeting had considered all the problem of GST and found solution for the problems.

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